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5 Aquatic organic matter decomposition in the terrestrial environments
6 of an intermittent headwater stream

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15 **Abstract**

16 Rivers and their riparian zones are linked by reciprocal subsidies such as leaf fall or the emergence of biphasic
17 aquatic organisms. Transfers of subsidies from freshwater to terrestrial ecosystems have been broadly studied, yet
18 few studies have explored the transfer of aquatic organic matter (AOM) to surrounding terrestrial ecosystems as a
19 response of hydrological variability. When rivers dry or flood, AOM can be transferred to terrestrial ecosystems
20 and decomposed by terrestrial organisms, however, this process remains poorly investigated. In this study, we
21 monitored the decomposition rate of several types of AOM (algae, macroinvertebrate and fish) exposed to different
22 drying intensity, on the gravel bars and in the riparian zone of an intermittent headwater stream. The contribution
23 of different terrestrial organisms to this decomposition rate was also explored. We showed that decomposition
24 rates did not differ between the gravel bars and riparian zone although the invertebrate assemblages, which
25 colonized the AOM, did. The decomposition rates depended mainly on the type of organic matter, with AOM of
26 animal origin being decomposed more rapidly than that of vegetal origin. Microorganisms and vertebrates
27 contributed most to the decomposition. Our results suggest that stranded AOM is consumed by terrestrial
28 organisms; however, environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity can affect its decomposition. As
29 extreme hydrological events are becoming more frequent, we need further research to explore how stranded AOM
30 decomposition changes across seasons, river types and climates to improve our understanding of this process and
31 its importance for terrestrial food webs.

32 **Key words:** intermittent-river, subsidies, drying-event, aquatic-organic-matter, decomposition

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38 **1. Introduction**

39 Rivers are dynamic ecosystems that drain water and materials from their surrounding terrestrial environments and
40 that sustain a unique and disproportionate amount of biodiversity in relation to their proportion on earth (Dudgeon
41 et al. 2006). They are characterized by spatial fluxes of organisms (e.g. macroinvertebrate, fishes), materials (e.g.
42 water, carbon) and energy (nutrients), linking different ecosystems, which together form a meta-ecosystem (Loreau
43 et al. 2003). Rivers interact with the riparian zone in a horizontal dimension linking the aquatic and terrestrial
44 habitats through subsidies, i.e. resources such as preys, detritus and nutrients that are transferred between a donor
45 and a recipient ecosystem (Richardson et al. 2010). For example, post-flood water draw-down (Bunn et al. 2006;
46 Sousa et al. 2012) and the emergence of biphasic life cycle aquatic organisms (e.g., insects and amphibians;
47 Regester et al. 2006; Schriever et al. 2014) enable the transfer of nutrients and carbon from the river to the riparian
48 zone and floodplain. These exchanges can be defined as aquatic-terrestrial subsidies (Baxter et al. 2005), whereas
49 organic matter that enters rivers through runoff, and leaf and terrestrial organism falls (Vannote et al. 1980;
50 Courtwright and May 2013; Milardi et al. 2015), can be defined as terrestrial-aquatic subsidies (Nakano and
51 Murakami 2001). Although less studied than terrestrial-aquatic subsidies, aquatic-terrestrial subsidies are of
52 significant importance for terrestrial ecosystems because they can represent a major part of their annual energy
53 budget (Baxter et al. 2005; Nakano and Murakami 2001).

54 Variations in the hydrological regime can result in the transfer of aquatic organic matter (AOM) towards adjacent
55 terrestrial habitats. For example, during floods the riparian zone and exposed riverine sediments (ERS; i.e.
56 relatively non-vegetated, within-channel deposited bars of silts, sands and gravels non-submerged when the river
57 is at base flow; Bates et al. 2007) can be submerged by water that transports dead organic matter, organisms and
58 sediments (Polis et al. 1997). When the water recedes, AOM may be stranded in terrestrial habitats and becomes
59 available for terrestrial consumers. Drying events may also promote transfers of AOM towards the terrestrial
60 environment. As in-channel water recedes during drying events, aquatic organisms which could not seek refuge in
61 perennial sections or the hyporheic zone can be stranded and die (Stanley et al. 1997; Boulton 2003). Drying events
62 can occur cyclically and predictably in intermittent rivers and streams; those rivers that cease to flow and dry at
63 some point in time and which represent more than half of the world's rivers by length (Datry et al. 2014; Messenger
64 et al. 2021). These watercourses are highly dynamic, with the alternation of wet and dry phases leading to the
65 expansion and contraction of terrestrial and aquatic habitats through time (Stanley et al. 1997). This high
66 hydrological variability often results in multiple phases of flooding and drying of the riverbed and riparian habitats,
67 which can promote transfers of aquatic subsidies into the terrestrial environment (Corti and Datry 2012; Steward
68 et al. 2012).

69 Studies dealing with the decomposition of AOM in terrestrial environments are scarce; focusing mainly on the
70 decomposition of anadromous species (e.g. salmon and lampreys) carcasses transported to the riparian zone by
71 large vertebrate predators and scavengers (e.g. bears, mink and river otters) and due to changes in hydrology (Ben-
72 David et al. 1998; Hilderbrand et al. 1999; Dunkle et al. 2020). Facultative vertebrate scavengers (i.e. non-obligate
73 scavengers that will occasionally feed on carcasses, such as rodents, corvids, foxes and martens) have also been
74 observed feeding on carcasses of aquatic organisms at the aquatic-terrestrial interface (Ben-David et al. 1997;
75 Schlichting et al. 2019). Invertebrates and microorganisms (bacteria and fungi) also play a key role in the
76 decomposition of terrestrial and aquatic organic matter (Chapin et al. 2002; Bruder et al. 2011; Hocking et al.

77 2009). Dry riverbeds are colonized by a specific set of organisms, mainly invertebrates attracted by newly freed
78 microhabitats and the high availability of stranded AOM at the water edge (Henshall et al. 2011). For example,
79 Bastow et al (2002), observed grasshoppers consuming stranded algae on drying riverbeds. Carabid *Coleoptera*,
80 especially from the *Bembidion* genus, have also been shown to feed on washed ashore aquatic insects (Hering and
81 Plachter 1997; Paetzold et al. 2005). Invertebrate communities differ between the riparian zone and dry riverbeds,
82 especially in intermittent rivers (Steward et al. 2011), suggesting that species decomposing the AOM and their
83 activity may differ among these habitats. However, little is known about the contribution of these different
84 assemblages to the decomposition of AOM across terrestrial habitats.

85 Another factor affecting the decomposition of AOM in terrestrial environment is the season at which the transfer
86 occurs, as the assemblage of scavenger organisms that will consume this matter might change throughout the year
87 (Power and Dietrich 2002). For example, organisms specialized in the consumption of stranded AOM on dry
88 riverbeds should be more abundant during seasons when drying typically occurs. This might especially be true for
89 the “clean-up crew” a community of organisms, mainly composed of invertebrates, that colonizes dry riverbeds at
90 the initiation of drying events and consume stranded and dying aquatic organisms (Steward et al. 2022). Besides,
91 several abiotic factors can influence decomposition; humidity and temperature being the most important. For
92 example, low humidity levels have been linked with a sharp decrease in the abundance of grasshoppers feeding on
93 algae (Bastow et al. 2002). Such preference for humid AOM could be due to its higher palatability, but also
94 attractiveness for organisms seeking water, particularly in very arid environment (McCluney & Sabo 2009). As
95 the intensity and duration of flooding and drying events will increase in the future (Trenberth 2011), so might the
96 exchanges between aquatic-terrestrial habitats. Therefore, it is crucial to understand how stranded AOM is
97 processed and transferred to terrestrial environments, especially considering that more than 50% of riparian
98 predator diets rely on aquatic subsidies across broad geographic regions (Lafage et al. 2019), even more so as
99 resources of aquatic origin are of higher nutritive quality than terrestrial ones (Twining et al. 2019).

100 In this study, we aimed 1) to measure the decomposition rates of aquatic organic matter (AOM) in the ERS of an
101 intermittent headwater stream and its adjacent riparian zone, and 2) to identify the relative contribution of major
102 groups of terrestrial decomposers involved in this process. First, we hypothesized (H1) that the decomposition rate
103 of the AOM would vary depending on the zone of deposition of the matter (i.e. riparian vs. ERS), due to local
104 differences in biotic and abiotic characteristics. We predicted a higher decomposition rate on the riparian zone
105 mainly due to a lesser exposure to flooding events allowing vegetation development and greater habitat stability,
106 which may sustain a higher diversity and abundance of decomposers (Steward et al. 2011, Corti and Datry 2016).
107 Second, we hypothesized that AOM of animal origin would be (H2) consumed faster than algae which are of lower
108 nutritive value and (H3) mainly decomposed by vertebrates and invertebrates. We then hypothesized (H4) that the
109 AOM decomposition rate lowers as drying duration increases because of its influence on organic matter moisture
110 content. Last, we hypothesized (H5) that the relative contribution of different major groups of terrestrial organisms
111 to the rate of AOM decomposition would differ depending on its desiccation level; due to a decrease in the interest
112 of vertebrates and invertebrates towards the dry AOM which, due to the drying process, will become less palatable
113 for these organisms.

114

115

116 2. Methods

117 2.1. Study site

118 The study was conducted in the upstream section of a small headwater stream: The Buizin, located in the east of
119 France, south of the Jura mountains. The Buizin is a 12km long stream and is one of the main tributaries of the
120 Albarine river (length: 59.4 km long), which flows into the Ain river (Corti and Datry 2012). The study site is an
121 intermittent section with a substrate dominated by bedrock (40%), cobbles (35%), gravels (15%) and boulders
122 (10%). Streambed drying at the site result from infiltrations caused by a porous karstic bedrock, and typically
123 occur in summer when precipitations are low and evapotranspiration is high. The study site was dry for 17 weeks
124 in 2020 based on a yearlong daily photo observation taken with camera traps permanently installed at the site.
125 These drying events occurred from late June to late November in 2020, interspersed with small rewetting events
126 linked to precipitation, lasting from a few days to a couple of weeks. Over-bank flooding events in the Buizin, are
127 scarce (1-2 per year) and usually occur in spring and early summer due to heavy precipitations coupled with snow
128 melt (Personal observation). The water level and the flow velocity were relatively low in early March (mean depth
129 21.5cm and mean flow velocity 0.394m/s, taken with a current meter at 11 points across a longitudinal transect)
130 exposing several non-vegetated gravel bars. In spring, a diverse community of aquatic invertebrates (**Table S1**)
131 and an abundant population of Salamander larvae (*Salamandra salamandra*; personal observation) inhabit the
132 stream. The mean minimal and maximal air temperature during the experiment were 1.3°C and 12.2°C,
133 respectively (data obtained from the nearest meteorological station). The Buizin is a shaded stream due to the
134 important tree canopy present in the riparian zone. This canopy was composed of *Acer pseudoplatanus*
135 (approximately 30% of the total tree species), *Corylus avellana* (25%), *Carpinus betulus* (25%), *Fraxinus excelsior*
136 (10%), and the remaining 10% was composed of others tree species (i.e. *Acer campestre* and *Fagus sylvatica*).
137 The riparian zone was also colonized by non-woody vegetation, mainly mosses, *Hedera.sp*, *Rubus.sp* and *Allium*
138 *ursinum*.

139 2.2. Organic matter decomposition experiment

140 A full factorial field experiment was performed in early March 2021 on a 40-meter-long section of the Buizin (**Fig.**
141 **1**) in two habitats (riparian vs. ERS) to assess the decomposition rate of the AOM from different origins (algae,
142 macroinvertebrate and fish), desiccation levels (dry vs. fresh) and exposed to different consumers (three different
143 mesh sizes preventing access to resources) at three sampling dates. Filamentous algae (Division: Chlorophyta),
144 chironomid larvae (Family: *Chironomidae*) and rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) were used as AOM types.
145 The AOM was selected based on its environmental relevance and ease of acquisition in large quantity. Chironomid
146 larvae and trouts are naturally present in the Buizin stream (**Table S1**), although trouts are only present 500 meters
147 downstream of the study site (Unpublished data). The algae naturally present in the Buizin stream in March are
148 not filamentous, however filamentous algae were chosen because they were more convenient to harvest in
149 sufficient quantity. Algae were harvested in experimental ponds at the Lyon 1 University campus (4.8679°;
150 45.7798°), then rinsed to remove sediments, organisms and debris; smaller debris were picked with pliers. Frozen
151 larvae of red Chironomids and fresh rainbow trout were bought from local suppliers. Our desiccation level
152 treatment consisted in comparing decomposition among dry vs fresh organic matter. For half of the samples
153 (n=162) 5g (\pm 0.1g) of algae (n=54), 10g (\pm 0.1g) of Chironomidae (n=54) and 15g (\pm 0.1g) of trout (boneless

154 muscle tissue; n=54), were dried at 90°C for 96 hours (dry treatment), to simulate a severe drying event (i.e. that
155 has lasted for several days or weeks) and then weighed to obtain their initial dry mass. For the other half, the same
156 mass was used but not dried (fresh treatment) to simulate a recent drying event (i.e. that occurred a few hours or
157 days ago). The mean ratio between humid and dry masses from the “dry treatment” was used to estimate the initial
158 dry mass of the “fresh treatment” for each AOM types. The organic matter was then placed in cylindrical aluminum
159 cups (7cm diameter for 1.7cm height) that were either unsealed, sealed with a 1cm coarse mesh, limiting the access
160 to vertebrates, or a 0.25mm fine mesh to prevent access to vertebrates and invertebrates. All cups were pierced at
161 the bottom (circle of 2cm diameter) to drain water in case of precipitation, the hole was covered with 0.25mm
162 mesh to prevent the loss of matter. As estimating the mass of AOM transferred from the aquatic environment to
163 the terrestrial environment during changes in hydrological regime is challenging, the initial masses were selected
164 to be sufficiently high, in order to allow the quantification of mass loss.

165 On March 4th, 27 cups were randomly placed on six different gravel bars and their adjacent riparian zones. Cups
166 were inserted into the sediments until they were flush to ground level. Two photo-traps with movement detection
167 were placed facing a gravel bar and its adjacent riparian zone in order to allow the identification of potential
168 vertebrates attracted by the AOM. Three coarse mesh, three fine mesh and three unsealed cups of each types of
169 dry and fresh organic matter (total=108) were randomly retrieved from the ERS and the riparian zone on day 4, 8
170 and 21 after the start of the experiment, in order to assess the decomposition rate of the organic matter. In the lab,
171 the organic matter was carefully rinsed above a 0.25 mm sieve with tap water and sorted to remove sediments,
172 invertebrates found during this process were preserved in 96% alcohol and later identified, mainly at the family
173 level. The organic matter was then dried at 90°C for 96 hours and weighed, then burned at 500°C for 1 hour to
174 quantify the ash free dry mass.

175 **2.3. Statistical analyses**

176 We used a Generalized Linear Mixed-Effect Model (GLMM) to compare the percent mass loss between the
177 removal dates (4 days, 8 days, 21 days), the desiccation levels (dry and fresh), the types of AOM (algae [A],
178 Chironomidae [C], fish [F]); the habitats (exposed riverine sediment [ERS] vs. riparian zone [RP]); and the mesh
179 sizes (0.25mm, 1cm and unsealed). We first used a global model in which we used site of deposition, corresponding
180 to the identity of the gravel bar and adjacent riparian patches, as the random intercept; all other variables (and
181 specific interactions) were fixed (see **Table 1** for model specifications). For each model, we used a binomial
182 distribution, and in case of overdispersion (i.e. when the observed response variance was greater than the
183 theoretical variance), a quasibinomial distribution (both with a logit link function) which are both fitted to the
184 analysis of proportional data. Similar results were obtained when using a beta distribution (**Table S2**). We used a
185 model averaging approach, comparing the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) of every model with each possible
186 variable combination, and averaging all models with a Δ AIC value threshold of 2 (i.e. selecting all models with
187 an AIC <2 from the model with the lowest AIC: “top model”). The model averaging approach was only performed
188 if more than one model was within the selected delta threshold; if no model was within a Δ AIC <2, we solely
189 selected the top model. The same approach was applied on subsets of data (e.g. a dataset containing only the algae
190 as AOM) to test specific hypotheses (H2, H3 and H4) that the global model, which was kept parsimonious (i.e.
191 avoiding to include overly complex interaction terms with more than two variables) could not test. Models obtained
192 from these subsets of data are hereafter referred as secondary models. Details on the models and variables used

193 are available in supplementary material (**Table S3**). Additional contrasts were used to compare differences in
194 response variables among each factor containing more than two levels, (e.g. for the removals dates, the second
195 removal date was used as intercept to specifically assess how much it differed from the third removal date).
196 Differences in invertebrate assemblages found in the cups were also assessed. Because the abundances were
197 relatively low, no transformation was applied to the data prior to the analyses. We used a Permutational
198 Multivariate Analysis of Variance using distance matrices (PERMANOVA) with the Bray Curtis dissimilarity
199 index to compare assemblages between the habitats (Anderson 2017). Assemblages were compared by separating
200 the cups by type of AOM resulting in a total of three groups (e.g. all invertebrates found in different cups containing
201 algae were considered to belong to the same group), that were subdivided by the desiccation level of the AOM and
202 the habitats (i.e., dry vs fresh; ERS vs RP). The different removal dates were combined to account for the low
203 abundance of invertebrates in the first and second removal dates. To take into account the loss of several cups due
204 to environmental conditions, each invertebrate abundance was divided by the number of cups retrieved in each
205 group. No invertebrates were found in cups containing dry algae in the ERS, thus, this group was removed from
206 the analyses.

207 A non-negligible number of cups were removed from analyses due to small rodent damages on cups sealed with
208 the 0.25mm and the 1cm mesh (n=28), and a small flood which occurred 3 days before the last removal date, which
209 submerged 2 gravel bars where cups were placed. Thus, 21 cups were submerged or lost during this flooding event
210 and were removed from the analyses. 8 samples were compromised during the laboratory processing, making a
211 total loss of 57 cups out of the 324 initials. All analyses were conducted on R studio (R version 4.0.3 (2020-10-
212 10)); *glmer* function in lme4 package (Bates et al. 2007) and *glmmPQL* function in the MASS package (Ripley et
213 al. 2013) were used for the GLMM with binomial distribution and with quasibinomial distribution, respectively.
214 *dredge* and *model.avg* functions in the MuMIn package (Barton et al. 2015) were used to perform the model
215 averaging analysis. For the invertebrate assemblage analyses the function *adonis* from the vegan package was used
216 (Oksanen et al., 2007); ggplot2 package was used for graphical representations (Wickham 2011)

217 **3. Results**

218 **3.1. Aquatic organic matter decomposition**

219 A single global model was selected during the averaging procedure (**Table 2**). The results of this global model
220 indicated that AOM mass loss differed depending on the type of AOM, the different removal dates, and certain
221 mesh sizes but did not respond to the desiccation level of the AOM and the habitat in which it was deposited
222 (**Table 2**). However, a significant interaction between mesh size and the desiccation level indicated differences in
223 decomposition between dry and fresh AOM in unsealed cups (**Table 2**).

224 **3.1.1. The decomposition rate of the AOM**

225 The total mass loss was higher for Chironomidae and fish than for algae, however no differences were found
226 between Chironomidae and fish (**Table 2**). Mass loss increased over time, especially for Chironomidae and fish,
227 which lost on average 3.66% and 3.57% of dry mass per day, respectively (**Fig. 2**). Chironomidae and fish had lost
228 on average 77% and 75% of their mass by the end of the experiment (**Fig. 2**). The mass loss measured at the second
229 and last removal dates were higher than at the first removal date for the Chironomidae AOM ($P < 0.01$ and $P < 0.001$,

230 respectively), whereas only the last mass loss measured was significantly higher than the first one for the fish
231 AOM ($P<0.01$), with a marked increase between the second and last removal dates. Algae total mass loss did not
232 change significantly over time (Table S4).

233 3.1.2. The contribution of terrestrial organisms depending on the type of AOM

234 No differences in mass loss were observed between the cups sealed with 0.25mm and 1cm mesh. Unsealed cups
235 however, had a significantly higher mass loss than the two other treatments (Table 2). A higher mass loss was
236 measured in unsealed cups containing fish and Chironomidae than in those containing algae (both $P<0.001$) (Fig.
237 3). However, no significant differences were observed between the mass loss of fish and Chironomidae in the
238 unsealed cups ($P>0.05$). The same pattern was observed in the cups sealed with the 1cm mesh, however, the mass
239 loss was significantly higher in cups that contained Chironomidae than fish ($P<0.001$). The mass loss was similar
240 between all types of AOM in cups sealed with the 0.25mm mesh (all $P>0.05$) (Fig. 3 and Table S5).

241 3.1.3. Desiccation level of the AOM

242 The desiccation level of the AOM did not affect the overall decomposition (Table 2). Secondary models indicated
243 that the desiccation level of the AOM did not affect the decomposition at each removal date (all $P<0.05$). When
244 each type of AOM was considered separately a higher mass loss was observed in dry fish than in fresh fish for the
245 second removal date ($P<0.01$), but not for the others removal dates, even if a tendency for a higher mass loss of
246 dry fish was observed (both $P>0.05$) (Table S6). Mass loss was similar across removal dates for the dry and fresh
247 treatment of the Chironomidae and algae AOM (Table S6). Regarding the contribution of different groups of
248 organisms on the decomposition of dry and fresh AOM, a higher mass loss was observed in dry AOM of unsealed
249 cups ($P<0.05$; Table 2). There were however no differences in decomposition rate in cups sealed with the 1cm
250 and 0.25mm meshes (both $P>0.05$).

251 3.2. Terrestrial assemblages

252 The camera traps captured the presence of small rodents around the cups and tooth marks on several empty cups
253 showed that these rodents were consuming the AOM, particularly dried fish (Fig. S1 and Fig. S2). A total of 141
254 invertebrates belonging to 23 different taxa were also found in the cups. *Coleoptera* represented 55.3% of the total
255 abundance (*Staphylinidae* [43.3%], *Carabidae* [9.2%] and *Dytiscidae* [2.8%]). The taxonomic richness was higher
256 in the cups that were placed in the riparian zone with 109 invertebrates belonging to 19 different taxa. Only 32
257 invertebrates belonging to 13 different taxa were found in the cups placed in the ERS. Among the 23 taxa found,
258 10 were only found in cups that were placed in the riparian zone, whereas 4 were only present in cups placed in
259 the ERS.

260 Regarding the type of AOM in which the invertebrates were found, in both habitats invertebrate abundance was
261 higher in cups containing fresh AOM than in those containing dry AOM (Fig. 4A). Woodlice from the
262 *Armadillidiidae* family were the most abundant in algae cups (n=7, 21.9%), whereas *Staphylinidae* beetles
263 composed most of the invertebrates found in Chironomidae cups (n=25, 55.6%) and fish cups (n=32, 50%);
264 *Carabidae* beetles were only found in cups containing fish (n=13, 20.3%). There was a similar pattern in both
265 habitats, with cups filled with algae containing less invertebrates (ERS=4, RP =28) than cups filled with
266 Chironomidae (ERS=11, RP =34) and fish (ERS=17, RP=47) (Fig. 4B). Invertebrate assemblage differed between

267 the ERS and RP cups ($P=0.02$). However, no differences were found, between dry and fresh AOM ($P=0.12$) and
268 the different type of AOM (Algae-Chironomidae: $P=0.94$, Algae-Fish: $P=0.61$, Chironomidae-Fish: $P=0.23$) in
269 both habitats.

270 **4. Discussion**

271 We assessed the decomposition rate of different types of aquatic organic matter (AOM) in two different terrestrial
272 habitats of an intermittent headwater stream, and quantified the contribution of large groups of terrestrial organisms
273 to this decomposition. We showed that AOM decomposition was similar between the habitats and depended
274 mainly on the type of organic matter, with AOM of animal origin being decomposed more rapidly than that of
275 vegetal origin. Microorganisms and vertebrates contributed most to the decomposition. Our results demonstrate
276 that different types of AOM are used as a resource by the terrestrial communities of intermittent rivers.

277 **4.1. Decomposition in the ERS and riparian habitats**

278 We expected differences in decomposition between the riparian and ERS habitats (H1) due to dissimilarities in
279 environmental factors such as light exposure, temperature, substrate and vegetation that typically foster the
280 establishment of distinct invertebrate communities between both habitats (Corti and Datry 2016). However, we
281 found no differences in the AOM decomposition rate or total mass loss, most likely due to a high homogeneity of
282 environmental conditions between the habitats at our study site. While in some rivers, ERS can be relatively
283 unshaded and exposed to high insolation leading to high temperatures (Steward et al. 2011), this may not be the
284 case in shaded headwater streams, such as the Buizin stream, where humidity and low temperature are preserved
285 by the tree canopy. Also, this study was conducted in early March when the Buizin was still flowing, light exposure
286 was low and air moisture and temperature were generally high and low, respectively. Such mild conditions may
287 not have created drastic differences between the ERS and the riparian zone, which could have induced similar
288 microbial decomposition rates among habitats, since temperature and moisture are key drivers of microbial activity
289 (Chapin et al. 2002). The only major differences between habitats were the substrate and the vegetation, which can
290 be important drivers of terrestrial invertebrate community composition (Steward et al. 2012; Corti and Datry 2016).
291 Despite no differences in decomposition, we found differences in the invertebrate assemblage composition,
292 diversity and abundance between habitats, confirming that different communities may inhabit riparian area and
293 ERS. Furthermore, the riparian zone and ERS at our site were separated by only a few meters. The ability of
294 vertebrates here, small rodents, to forage for food at distances exceeding several tens of meters (Anderson 1986;
295 Den Ouden et al. 2005), might explain the similarity in the vertebrate-driven decomposition. Thus, several biotic
296 and abiotic factors can affect the decomposition of stranded AOM in terrestrial environment, implying that the fate
297 of the AOM may vary depending on the characteristics of the environment in which it is deposited (Siebers et al.
298 2021).

299 **4.2. The contribution of the different groups of organisms to the decomposition rates**

300 Each type of AOM was decomposed in the terrestrial environment; however, their decomposition rate and total
301 mass loss varied. As predicted (H2), we found a higher decomposition rate for AOM of animal origins in
302 comparison to vegetal origins. The rapid decomposition of AOM of animal origins suggests that algae could be
303 less appealing to terrestrial organisms, especially invertebrates and vertebrates, as the total mass loss of algae did

304 not differ regardless of the mesh size used on the cups. Thus, microorganisms were probably driving the
305 decomposition of algae. This can potentially be explained by the low nutritive value and digestibility of
306 filamentous algae in comparison to AOM of animal origins (Peterson et al. 1998; Kahlert et al. 2002). Filamentous
307 algae can proliferate when water temperature increases and water velocity decreases (Dahm et al. 2003), which is
308 usually occurring before complete drying in intermittent rivers (Lake 2003); this raises the question of the fate of
309 stranded filamentous algae in intermittent rivers, especially if drying event occurs when invertebrate activity is
310 low. However, our study design does not consider the potential leaching of nutrients from the AOM, which might
311 represent a non-negligible transfer of nutrient of aquatic origins toward the terrestrial environment, especially for
312 AOM that is not rapidly consumed by terrestrial organisms.

313 In general, microorganisms and vertebrates drove AOM decomposition (H3), while invertebrate contribution was
314 low as indicated by the absence of differences in the total mass loss of AOM between cups sealed with the 1cm
315 and 0.25mm mesh. However, the higher mass loss of AOM of animal origins in the 1cm sealed cups and the
316 presence of known invertebrate scavengers and detritivores such as several *Coleoptera* and *Armadillidiidae*
317 (Hering and Plachter 1997; Hering 1998; Warburg 1987) in the cups (1cm mesh and unsealed) suggests that
318 invertebrates did consume the AOM. In fact, the most represented taxa found in cups were *Coleoptera* from the
319 *Carabidae* and *Staphylinidae* family who are known scavengers (Lövei and Sunderland 1996; Newton et al. 2000),
320 and were, as expected, mostly found on AOM of animal origins (Paetzold et al. 2005). It is unlikely that these
321 organisms are specialized towards the decomposition of fish; as fish is not naturally present in this section of the
322 Buizin stream, suggesting that the fish AOM, attracted opportunistic invertebrate scavengers. In the cups
323 containing algae, the most prevalent taxa were from the *Armadillidiidae* family, whose main food source is
324 composed of vegetal detritus (Warburg 1987). These results suggest that specific invertebrate assemblages may
325 be attracted by specific types of organic matter. However, we found no differences in the invertebrate assemblages
326 depending on the types of AOM present in the cups. The invertebrate contribution to the decomposition must have
327 been too low to be differentiated from that of microorganisms, explaining the absence of differences in the AOM
328 total mass loss. This low contribution of invertebrates is counterintuitive, as they have been shown to play an
329 important role in the decomposition of AOM in terrestrial environments (Novais et al. 2015; Hocking et al. 2009).
330 This could however be explained by the cold and humid weather of early March, which led to a low invertebrate
331 activity (Driessen et al. 2013), resulting in the low contribution of invertebrates towards the decomposition of the
332 AOM.

333 Environmental conditions, especially temperature, vary throughout the year, leading to changes in invertebrate
334 communities and activity, including decomposer assemblages (Driessen et al. 2013). These changes affecting the
335 decomposer assemblages will have an impact on their contribution to the organic matter decomposition, resulting
336 in longer decomposition rate in winter than in warmer seasons, due to lower temperature and invertebrate activity
337 in the former (Castro et al. 2013). Lower temperatures have also been linked to a decrease in the decomposition of
338 organic matter by microorganisms (Stott et al. 1986). It is therefore highly likely that the decomposition rate of
339 AOM would have been higher in late spring and summer, due to a higher temperature leading to an increase in
340 decomposer activity. Others studies focusing on the seasonal variability of the AOM decomposition in terrestrial
341 environment are thus needed, to fully assess the fate of stranded AOM in terrestrial environments. This, especially
342 considering that climate change will cause shifts from perennial to intermittent regimes and changes in the

343 seasonality of drying in intermittent rivers (with earlier and more frequent drying events; Döll & Schmied 2012;
344 Sauquet et al. 2021), which could create mismatches between AOM availability and consumer community activity.

345 **4.3. Humidity level of the AOM**

346 Contrary to what we expected, the desiccation level of the AOM had little impact on the decomposition rate (H4).
347 Our treatment only affected the fish AOM and only at the second removal date, where the dry fish had a higher
348 mass loss than the fresh fish. Dry fish is the only type of AOM that was completely consumed by the end of the
349 experiment in unsealed cups, showing its high appeal for vertebrates, small rodents in our case. This is partially
350 confirmed by the fact that the mass loss was higher for dried AOM in unsealed cups that were used to quantify the
351 contribution of vertebrates (H5). This preference for dry fish might be explained by the humid weather that re-
352 humidified the dried AOM, erasing the initial difference in humidity level. Due to ambient moisture, it is also
353 likely that fresh fish (on which microbial community was not reset to zero by the drying treatment) was exposed
354 to a rapid microbial colonization and activity resulting in its putrefaction, which potentially repelled the rodents.
355 The smell of carrion can attract necrophagous insects (Weithmann et al. 2020), which could explain the highest
356 abundance of invertebrates found in cups containing fresh fish. It is possible that under environmental conditions
357 that would have kept the initial desiccation level of the AOM constant, our results would have been more similar
358 to the ones from previous studies, where desiccated matter was less consumed than humid matter (Bastow et al.
359 2002; Collins and Baxter 2014). Microbial decomposition was similar between dry and fresh AOM, probably due
360 to a fast recolonization of the dry AOM following ambient re-humidification. It is however possible that dry AOM
361 is colonized by a different microbial community than fresh AOM, as we observed different types of molds between
362 dry and fresh Chironomidae at the last removal date (**Fig. S3**). The presence of these molds, only at the last removal
363 date, might indicate a longer colonization and degradation time by microbial communities for this type of AOM.

364 Our results suggest that after a drying event occurring during a relatively cold period, the colonization and
365 degradation of AOM by microorganisms and vertebrates will be important, as the matter will still be humid in the
366 early stages of drying (Foulquier et al. 2015; Collins and Baxter 2014). As drying continues and the humidity level
367 of the matter diminishes, a decrease in decomposition would occur, potentially followed by a shift in the
368 assemblage of decomposers. Such results have been observed by Novais et al. (2015), on invertebrate decomposer
369 communities of an invasive clam species deposited on the riparian zone by a flooding event. Therefore, after a
370 drying event, microorganisms and invertebrates may rapidly start the breakdown of the stranded AOM until the
371 environmental conditions lead to complete desiccation of the AOM, making it less palatable for these organisms.
372 Vertebrates can also consume dried AOM from animal origin, in addition to humid AOM at the start of the drying
373 event (Paetzold et al. 2008), before its putrefaction. Thus, the AOM decomposition rate in terrestrial habitats of
374 intermittent rivers will vary depending on the characteristics of a drying event (e.g. duration, severity). Hence,
375 depending on these characteristics, different consumer guilds might be favored, and food webs modified depending
376 on the duration of the drying event. Such effects of drying duration have notably been evidenced for leaf litter
377 decomposition in the aquatic environment (Datry et al. 2011; Corti et al. 2011). The fact that this study was done
378 on a single site in early spring with a relatively limited number of replicates prevents much generalization. Other
379 studies are thus needed across several rivers with different environmental characteristics (e.g. intermittence
380 gradient, tree canopy, substrate, drying duration) and at different seasons to improve our knowledge on the fate of

381 aquatic organic matter on terrestrial habitats and its importance as a resource for terrestrial communities throughout
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393 **Availability of data**

394 The dataset analyzed in this study are available at Figshare via the following links : [10.6084/m9.figshare.17049821](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.17049821)
395 and [10.6084/m9.figshare.17049824](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.17049824)

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647 **Tables**

648 **Table 1:** Description of the variables used in the different models and the question they address

Variable	Description	Level	Question answered
Removal dates	Dates of retrieval of the cups (Day 4, Day 8, and Day 21)	Sample	Do decomposition rates of the different types of AOM vary through time?
Desiccation level	Humidity level of the AOM (dry = desiccated matter and fresh = non-desiccated matter)	Sample	Does the decomposition rate differs depending on the AOM humidity level?
AOM	Type of aquatic organic matter used (Algae, Chironomidae and Fish)	Sample	Does the decomposition rate vary among different types of AOM?
Habitat	Habitat in which the AOM was exposed (ERS = Exposed Riverine Sediment and RP = Riparian zone)	Site	Does the decomposition rate differ among the habitats?
Mesh size	Mesh diameter used (0.25mm, 1cm and unsealed = absence of mesh recovering the cups)	Sample	Does the contribution of different organisms to the decomposition differ?
Sites	Randomly selected patches of riparian zone and ERS where the cups were placed	Site	Is decomposition affected by the patch identity?
Interactions			
Desiccation level vs Mesh size	Desiccation level*Mesh size	Sample	Does the contribution of the different groups of terrestrial organisms vary depending on the humidity level of the AOM?
AOM vs Mesh size	AOM*Mesh size	Sample	Does the contribution of the different groups of terrestrial organisms vary depending on the type of AOM?

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654 **Table 2:** Results from the global generalized linear mixed effect model. Only one model was
 655 selected during the model averaging process. Contrast change results corresponds to the
 656 same model but with different reference level. Unmentioned levels were the ones used as
 657 reference. Interactions are highlighted in italic.

Variables	Estimate	P-value
Intercept	-8.367	<0.001 ***
Mesh size (1cm)	0.539	0.623
Mesh size (unsealed)	4.386	<0.001 ***
AOM (Chironomidae)	5.055	<0.001 ***
AOM (Fish)	4.212	<0.001 ***
Removal dates (8 days)	1.235	0.017 *
Removal dates (21 days)	3.764	<0.001 ***
Desiccation level (fresh)	1.262	0.191
<i>Mesh size (1cm) : Desiccation level (fresh)</i>	-0.632	0.621
<i>Mesh size (unsealed) : Desiccation level (fresh)</i>	-2.856	0.013 *
Contrast change		
Intercept	-1.968	0.013 *
Mesh size (0.25mm)	0.103	0.925
Mesh size (unsealed)	4.340	<0.001 ***
AOM (Algae)	-4.428	<0.001 ***
AOM (Fish)	-0.685	0.128
Removal dates (4 days)	-1.345	0.01 *
Removal dates (21 days)	2.552	<0.001 ***
Desiccation level (fresh)	0.999	0.265
<i>Mesh size (0.25mm) : Desiccation level (fresh)</i>	0.059	0.963
<i>Mesh size (unsealed) : Desiccation level (fresh)</i>	-2.889	0.008 **

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661 **Figures**

662 **Fig. 1** Map of the Albarine river catchment, showing the location of the study site and the
663 repartition of the different gravel bars and riparian zones used in this experiment

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672 **Fig. 2** Kinetic of the decomposition (mean \pm SD) of the different types of aquatic organic
 673 matter. Samples from the ERS and the riparian zone were combined as no significant
 674 differences were found between the two habitats (mean \pm SD). Different letters indicate
 675 significant differences between the type of AOM within each removal date; comparisons
 676 between the removal dates can be found in Table 2. Post hoc comparison within each removal
 677 date were obtained using a model containing only the AOM variable as predictor.

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Aquatic Organic Matter (AOM)

684 **Fig. 3** Mass loss of the different types of AOM depending on the meshes applied to the cups, n
 685 = 84 for the 0.25 mm mesh, n = 85 for the 1cm mesh, n = 98 for cups without mesh. Different
 686 letters indicate significant differences between the type of AOM (all $P < 0.001$). Differences
 687 between the mesh sizes can be found in Table 2.

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698 **Fig. 4 A)** Abundance of invertebrates found inside the cups in the exposed riverine sediments
 699 (ERS) and the riparian zone (RP) as a function of the type of treatment (Dry and Fresh).
 700 **B)** Abundance of invertebrates found inside the cups in the dry riverbed ERS and RP as a
 701 function of the type of organic matter present inside the cups

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711 **Supplementary Information**

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713 **Table S1:** Macroinvertebrate abundance of the Buizin stream in March 2021. Invertebrate
 714 were sampled at 10 location, proportionally representing all benthic habitats, using a 500 µm
 715 mesh size surber sampler (0.5m²).

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Order	Genus	Abundance
Diptera	<i>Pediciidae Gen. sp.</i>	1
Diptera	<i>Limoniidae Gen. sp.</i>	1
Diptera	<i>Psychodidae Gen. sp.</i>	1
Diptera	<i>Simuliidae Gen. sp.</i>	9
Diptera	<i>Chironomidae Gen. sp.</i>	14
Trichoptera	<i>Micropterna sp.</i>	12
Trichoptera	<i>Stenophylax sp.</i>	23
Trichoptera	<i>Drusus sp.</i>	1
Trichoptera	<i>Rhyacophila sp.</i>	5
Trichoptera	<i>Plectrocnemia sp.</i>	5
Trichoptera	<i>Agapetus sp.</i>	1
Ephemeroptera	<i>Rhithrogena sp.</i>	8
Ephemeroptera	<i>Habrophlebia sp.</i>	5
Ephemeroptera	<i>Baetis sp.</i>	3
Ephemeroptera	<i>Alainites sp.</i>	2
Crustacea	<i>Gammarus sp.</i>	8
Plecoptera	<i>Brachyptera sp.</i>	208
Plecoptera	<i>Nemoura sp.</i>	3
Plecoptera	<i>Capnia sp.</i>	76
Plecoptera	<i>Isoperla sp.</i>	19
Plecoptera	<i>Perlodidae Gen. sp.</i>	6
Coleoptera	<i>Agabus sp. Lv.</i>	1

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734 **Table S2:** Comparison of the estimates and p-values of the global generalized linear mixed
 735 effect model with a Binomial distribution and a Beta distribution. Contrast change results
 736 corresponds to the same model but with different contrast level. Unmentioned levels were the
 737 ones used as reference.

Variables	Binomial distribution		Beta distribution	
	Estimate	P-value	Estimate	P-value
Intercept	-8.367	<0.001 ***	-2.065	<0.001 ***
Mesh size (1cm)	0.539	0.623	0.394	0.124
Mesh size (unsealed)	4.386	<0.001 ***	1.988	<0.001 ***
AOM (Chironomidae)	5.055	<0.001 ***	1.351	<0.001 ***
AOM (Fish)	4.212	<0.001 ***	1.607	<0.001 ***
Removal dates (8 days)	1.235	0.017 *	0.373	0.017 *
Removal dates (21 days)	3.764	<0.001 ***	1.041	<0.001 ***
Desiccation level (fresh)	1.262	0.191	0.282	0.252
Mesh size (1cm) : Desiccation level (fresh)	-0.632	0.621	-0.523	0.128
Mesh size (unsealed) : Desiccation level (fresh)	-2.856	0.013 *	-1.088	<0.001 ***
Contrast change				
Intercept	-1.968	0.013 *	0.053	0.811
Mesh size (0.25mm)	0.103	0.925	-0.394	0.124
Mesh size (unsealed)	4.340	<0.001 ***	1.595	<0.001 ***
AOM (Algae)	-4.428	<0.001 ***	-1.351	<0.001 ***
AOM (Fish)	-0.685	0.128	0.256	0.1
Removal dates (4 days)	-1.345	0.01 *	-0.373	0.017 *
Removal dates (21 days)	2.552	<0.001 ***	0.668	<0.001 ***
Desiccation level (fresh)	0.999	0.265	-0.241	0.316
Mesh size (0.25mm) : Desiccation level (fresh)	0.059	0.963	0.523	0.128
Mesh size (unsealed) : Desiccation level (fresh)	-2.889	0.008 **	-0.565	0.069

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740 **Table S3:** Variable selected in the secondary models to test the different hypothesis

Subset of data used for the secondary models	Removal date	Dessiccation level	Mesh size	AOM	Site	Hypothesis tested
AOM = Algae	X				X	H2
AOM = Chironomidae	X				X	H2
AOM = Fish	X				X	H2
Mesh size = 0.25mm				X	X	H3
Mesh size = 1cm				X	X	H3
Mesh size = unsealed				X	X	H3
Removal dates = 4 days		X		X	X	H4
Removal dates = 8 days		X		X	X	H4
Removal dates = 21 days		X		X	X	H4

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742 The data were subdivided to test the different hypothesis. The different variables and subset of
743 data were selected accordingly to their relevance to the targeted hypothesis.

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745 **Table S4:** Results obtained in the secondary models focusing on H2

Variables	AOM Algae		AOM Chironomidae		AOM Fish	
	Estimate	P-value	Estimate	P-value	Estimate	P-value
	AIC: 34.6		AIC: 86.8		AIC: 99.9	
Intercept	-3.526	<0.001 ***	-1.871	<0.001 ***	-1.099	0.007 **
Removal dates (8 days)	-0.029	0.984	1.635	0.010 *	0.234	0.69
Removal dates (21 days)	0.348	0.809	5.13	<0.001 ***	2.261	<0.001 ***
Contrast change						
Intercept	-3.555	<0.001 ***	-0.236	0.494	-0.865	0.040 *
Removal dates (4 days)	0.029	0.984	-1.635	0.01 *	-0.234	0.691
Removal dates (21 days)	0.377	0.793	3.495	0.001 **	2.028	0.002 **

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Table S5: Results obtained in the secondary models focusing on H3

Variables	Mesh size: 0.25mm		Mesh size: 1cm		Mesh size: unsealed	
	AIC: 69.9		AIC: NA		AIC: 109.4	
	Estimate	P-value	Estimate	P-value	Estimate	P-value
Intercept	-34.17	0.939	-1.528	<0.001 ***	-2.234	<0.001 ***
AOM (Chironomidae)	33.53	0.940	1.559	<0.001 ***	3.0667	<0.001 ***
AOM (Fish)	32.83	0.941	0.782	<0.001 ***	3.109	<0.001 ***
Contrast change						
Intercept	-6.419e-01	0.1	0.031	0.808	0.833	0.028
AOM (Algae)	-3.433e+01	1	-1.559	<0.001 ***	-3.066	<0.001 ***
AOM (Fish)	-6.931e-01	0.276	-0.776	<0.001 ***	0.043	0.936

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753 AIC = NA is due to the use of a quasibinomial distribution for the respective model.

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Table S6: Results obtained in the secondary models focusing on H4

Variables	Removal dates (4 days)		Removal date (8 days)		Removal date (21 days)	
	AIC: 77.1, 78.1, 79.0		AIC: NA		AIC: NA	
	Estimate	P-value	Estimate	P-value	Estimate	P-value
Intercept	-8.494	0.928	-1.647	<0.001 ***	-1.332	<0.001 ***
Desiccation level (fresh)	4.980	0.958	2.351	<0.001 ***	30.916	0.99
Desiccation level (fresh): AOM (Chironomidae)	-5.189	0.956	-0.607	0.235	0.198	0.735
Desiccation level (fresh): AOM (Fish)	-5.492	0.954	-1.593	0.004 **	-28.969	0.99
Contrast change						
Intercept	-1.780	0.004 **	0.292	0.241	1.009	0.002
Desiccation level (fresh): AOM (Algae)	3.2325	0.981	0.607	0.235	-0.198	0.735
Desiccation level (fresh): AOM (Fish)	-0.303	0.732	-0.987	0.049*	-28.166	0.99

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757 AIC = NA is due to the use of a quasibinomial distribution for the respective model, several

758 AIC values correspond to the AIC values of the selected models that were used for the model

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averaging process.

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765 **Fig. S1** Photos from the camera trap facing the aluminum cups placed in a gravel bars, red
766 circles highlight rodents near aluminum cups

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780 **Fig. S2** Damaged and emptied sealed (0.25mm) aluminum cup that contained dried fish

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785 **Fig. S3:** Different types of molds found on the Chironomidae AOM after 21 days, fresh
786 Chironomidae (left) and dry Chironomidae (right).